

THE CHALLENGES FACING COMMERCIAL MOTORCYCLE OCCUPATION IN ETSAKO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the challenges facing commercial motorcycle occupation in Edo State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was adopted. Data were collected through questionnaires and in-depth interviews (IDIs) among selected motorcyclists, police officers and road safety officials in Etsako West Local Government Area, Edo State. A total of 255 questionnaires were administered and 10 in-depth interviews were conducted. Data analyses involved univariate and content analyses. The findings revealed that social stigmatization due to the use of motorcycles for criminal activities, lack of protection and inadequate clothing for riders, recklessness, impatience, over speeding and non-compliance to traffic rules, ban and arrest of innocent motorcyclists and payment of incessant levies are the major challenges of commercial motorcyclists in Etsako West, Edo State. The findings were discussed with reference to relevant empirical literatures, and with recommendations both for practice and future research highlighted.

Key words: Challenges, Commercial motorcycles, Motorcyclists, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria attempted the process of economic liberalization in 1986 with the advent of the Structural Adjustment Programme which led to major restructuring of formal sector activities that has impact on the informal sector in various ways. Cost cutting strategies of formal sector organizations and industrial units led to job losses in the sector while the losers have had to take up alternative means of livelihood in the informal sector of the economy (Ogunrinola, 2011). The informal sector has thus become a major provider of employment especially in developing and transitional economies (Khotkina, 2007).

The types of work available in the informal sector are diverse and multifarious. It stretches from casual and unstable employment like garbage picking, street trading, domestic help, transportation, commercial motorcycling and so on. Commercial motorcyclists popularly known as Okada riders in Nigeria are motorcycle operators who carry passengers for hire. It is one of the most common forms of informal occupation among unemployed males in Nigeria. Its popularity and widespread acceptance has rapidly risen in recent years. Unfortunately, the rise has been accompanied by increased levels of risk of accidents, bad behaviours, reckless riding, poor attitude of the operators and resistance to laudable government policies among others (Akpan et., al 2011; Olubomehin, 2012). As a result, they have come under heavy scrutiny culminating in legislations restricting and in some instances prohibiting their operations in some cities. This in effect shrinks the economic and social benefits derived from the use of motorcycles for commercial purposes.

A vibrant economy usually is categorized by the rate of commercial activities going on within the system. It is equally characterized by the number of active youths who are self-employed and not relying only on the government for white collar jobs or job creation. Thus, commercial motorcycling are readily available means of livelihood to many unemployed youths (graduates and undergraduates), retirees and illiterates in Nigeria (Solagberu et, al 2006; Gbadamosi 2006; Arosayin et., al 2011). As such, commercial motorcycle business serves as means for engaging people for the purpose of socio-economic development. It is

upon this reality, the study examines the challenges of commercial motorcycling business in Edo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Commercial motorcyclists in Nigeria and many other developing countries are faced with numerous challenges. One of the outstanding challenges is the health related problem. This is due to the fact that commercial motorcyclists (Okada riders) operate under unkind weather conditions which often result in illnesses such as fever, headache, back ache, respiratory diseases, and chest pain to mention but few. These illnesses are harmful and detrimental to their wellbeing.

Also, considering the poor state of infrastructural facilities in Nigeria, majority of commercial motorcyclists operate on bad roads with several potholes and poor drainage systems which lead to regular road accidents especially during raining season. It is due to the increasing rate of road accidents and other social issues caused by motorcycles some State authorities prohibited the operation of commercial motorcycles within their territory. In other states, the operation of commercial motorcycles was restricted to certain hours of the day (Akpan et. al 2011) which has economic and social implications on the lives of people and the nation.

More so, commercial motorcyclists are sometimes perceived as perpetrators of dubious dealings, double-crossing of innocent passengers: snatching of personal belongings like bags, phones, abduction and killing as well as raping of innocent girls. (Nigerian news world, 2nd July, 2011). Consequently, commercial motorcyclists are often faced with social stigmatization and harassment from law enforcement officers with unlawful arrest by police officers because of bribe and corruption (Olubomehin 2012; Akpan et., al 2011). As well, it was discovered that commercial motorcyclists paid exorbitant dues to the local government authorities as well as their associations. This in effect, led to situation where passengers are asked to pay high fare which often brings up conflict or public riot in Nigeria.

All of these challenges hindered the growth of commercial motorcycle business in Nigeria which becomes issue of concern for peace loving Nigerians, researchers and voluntary associations, particularly Non-Governmental Organizations who give out motorcycles on hire purchase or instalment to unemployed youths, retirees, and illiterates and civil servants etc. as a way to reduce youth restiveness and promote poverty eradication programmes and economic survival for sustainable development.

Research Objectives

While many Nigeria researchers have studied the issue of safety, income and employment generation, poverty reduction as well as the occupational expectation of commercial motorcyclists (Ogunrinola, 2011; Folawewo, 2006 and Olufayo 2006), study to document the challenges of commercial motorcyclists in Nigeria is almost absent. Therefore, this study set out to fill this gap by investigating the challenges of commercial motorcyclists in Etsako West Local Government Area (LGA), Edo State, Nigeria.

Arising from the observe problems above, the objectives of this study are to:

- i. Examine the challenges associated with activities of commercial motorcycling in Edo State, Nigeria
- ii. Investigate the influence of the challenges facing commercial motorcyclist on socio-economic development in Edo State, Nigeria
- iii. Investigate the level of job satisfaction among commercial motorcyclists in Edo State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study centered on challenges of commercial motorcycling business in Etsako West Local Government Area of Edo state, Nigeria. The study includes all classes of commercial motorcyclists; full-time and part time riders, in selected wards within the Etsako LGAs. A descriptive survey design with the aid of self-administered questionnaire and in-depth interview were used. The consideration for descriptive survey design is based on the fact that it allows researchers to observe phenomenon without manipulating or controlling any of the variables.

Study Area

This study was carried out in Etsako West Local Government Area of Edo State. Etsako West is in the south-south region of Nigeria. It is made up of five clans; Uzairue, Auchi, South-Ibie, Awain and Agbede as well as ten geopolitical wards which includes; Auchi, Jattu, South-ibie, Aviele, Agbede, Afashio, Awain, Ikabigbo, Ayogwiri, and Uwarrake. It has an area of 946km, and approximate population of 197,609 based on the 2006 census. Moreover, Etsako West is predominantly a composition of Christian and Islamic religion. More so, road transport which include private and commercial motor vehicles, motorcycles and tricycles are the major means of transportation in Etsako West LGAs.

Population of the Study

The population of the study covered all classes of commercial motorcyclists; both full-time and part-time operators in Etsako West Local Government of Edo State with the exception of commercial motorcyclists who do not have attachment to any specific unit. Balloting sampling method was used to select four out of the ten wards in Etsako LGAs as the study area. The study also, included the executives of motorcyclist unions in Etsako LGAs.

Table 1: Numbers of commercial motorcycle operators in selected wards

Wards	Survey Unit	No. of operator	No. Selected to administer questionnaire	No. of Retrieved Questionnaire
Jattu	Jattu market unit	47	24	22
	Oghieneni Unit	45	23	23
	Ighiku unit	44	22	22
	Imeke Unit	12	12	10
Auchi	waterboard unit	40	20	20
	Igbe road unit	40	20	20
	AP unit	45	23	19
	Uwarrake unit	22	11	08
South-Ibie	Auchi poly unit	50	25	23
	Powerline unit	40	20	17
	Ivherekhu unit	30	15	14
	Sabo Unit	24	12	12
Afashio	Apovha unit	25	13	12
	Notre Dame unit	30	15	12
	Iyora unit	20	10	09
	St Angela unit	25	13	12
Total		550	278	255

Source: Field Survey (2013)

Sample Size

The calculation for sample size was based on the consideration to examine at least half (50%) of the total study population. Thus, a sample of two hundred and seventy-eight (278)

respondents were sampled which represented 50.5% of the total population selected through triangulation of sampling methods and cuts across all the selected units from each selected wards. But only two hundred and fifty-five (255) questionnaires were retrieved for data analysis, which represented 46.3% of the total population and 91.7% response rate as shown in table 1 above.

Sampling Procedure

A multi-stage sampling approach was adopted for the selection of the respondents. The consideration for multi-stage sampling is based on the fact that respondents cut across different wards and units within Etsako West Local Government of Edo State. There are ten wards – Auchi, jattu, Afashio, Agbede, Ivhiele, Ikabigbo, Ayogwiri, South Ibie, Awain, and Uwarrake. However, four wards were randomly selected using simple random method. Also, completed lists of all the units of commercial motorcyclists under the selected wards were collected from their headquarters.

Thereafter, all units under selected wards were assigned numbers and four units were simple random technique. This was done to minimize bias and ensure equal representation of units in the study. Moreover, respondents in each unit were selected through balloting sampling, members of the selected units were asked to pick numbers randomly which qualify them to participate in the study. Importance was placed on those who have been in Okada business for not less than five years and knowledgeable enough to understand the questions on the research instrument during balloting process. The consideration is to achieve the objective of the study with no deficiency. Afterward, questionnaire was administered to the respondents to generate quantitative data while in- depth interviews was conducted among some selected union executives.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The needed data was obtained through primary source and this involved the use of both questionnaire and in-depth interview. The consideration for combining both questionnaire and in-depth interview is to fully capture the phenomena understudy.

The questionnaire was structured and consisted of questions with options from which respondents are expected to pick response as applicable (close-ended) and questions which allow respondents to freely express their opinion on the subject matter (open-ended). In addition, thirty percent of the questions are open-ended while seventy percent are closed-ended questions. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire was ascertained by conference of scholars in social sciences for content and construct validity. Also, the Cronbach alpha of instrument was 0.87 which indicate that the instrument is valid and reliable.

Also, in-depth interviews with average length of 15 minutes were conducted among some selected union executives, police officers and road safety officials in the units understudy. An interview guide containing set of questions relating to the subject matter was used as a plan to keep the conversation focused on the subject matter, while giving the interviewees room to freely express their perception on the content of discussion.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The study employed both descriptive (that is, frequency distribution and simple percentages) and content analyses.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical consideration was emphasized throughout the field work. Participation of respondents was based on informed and voluntary consents. The respondents were at liberty to discontinue their participation at any point during the exercise, their confidentiality and opinion regarding questions perception was fully respected.

4.0 Result and Discussion

4.1 Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Results of socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents as presented in Table 2 showed that all the respondents were male representing 100%. This shows that the motorcycle (Okada) business is a male oriented profession in Nigeria. Also, most respondents (31.6%) fell within 26 to 30 years, (17.8%) fell within 36-40 years, (17.4%) fell within 31-35 years, (16.6%) fell within 21-25 years, (8.7%) fell within 15-20 years while the least (7.9%) fell within 40 years and above. This result shows that majority of commercial motorcyclists are economically-active population, which supports the view of Solagberu et, al (2006) who noted that bulk of motorcycle operators were young men.

Table 2: Showing the demographic characteristics of the respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	255	100.0
Total	255	100.0
Age	Frequency	Percentage
15-20	22	8.7
21-25	42	16.6
26-30	80	31.6
31-35	44	17.4
36-40	45	17.8
41 and above	20	7.9
Total	253	100.0
Marital status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	91	35.7
Married	164	64.3
Total	255	100.0
Religion Affiliation	Frequency	Percentage
Christian	183	71.8
Islam	72	28.2
Total	255	100.0
Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
No formal education	41	16.1
Primary	43	16.9
Secondary	95	37.3
OND/NCE	24	9.4
Bsc/HND	52	20.3
Total	255	100.0
State of Origin	Frequency	Percentage
Edo	101	39.6
Delta	44	17.3
Rivers	43	16.9
Others	67	17.3
Total	255	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2013)

The marital status of respondents showed that 35.7% were single while the married constituted 64.3% of the total respondents. This goes to reinforce the fact that most of the participants were married and have family responsibilities. The finding supports the view of Gbadamosi (2006) who stressed the significance of commercial motorcycling on family live and sustenance.

Furthermore, the religious affiliation of the respondents showed that 71.8% were Christians while 28.2% were Muslims. Thus, it can be inferred that there are more Christians than Muslims among the respondents which may be due to the predominance of Christians in the study area. This is apparent in the differences in percentage between Christian and Islamic religion. However, it can be sustained that since the percentage of Christian faithful was highest in the study area, Weber's ideology must be valid, which provided the link between religion of Christianity and hard work for economic achievement and sustainability.

With respect to the educational qualification of respondents, as shown on the table 2, 16.1% of the respondents have no formal education; 16.9% possessed primary school certificates; 37.3% of the respondents possessed secondary school certificate; 9.4% possessed Ordinary National Diploma and National Certified Education; while 20.3% of the respondents have Bachelor degree/Higher National Diploma. This shows that there were individuals with higher academic qualifications such as bachelor degree who engaged in the operation of commercial motorcycle business in Etsako Local Government Area. This supports the view of preceding scholars in the literature that argued that the engagement of Nigerian graduates in Okada business could be due to dwindling economic problem. Some writers have expressed deep concern on the trend of graduate involvement, while some have appreciated the trend as functional to the economic sustenance of the Nigerian Graduate. However, what can be explained in this table is that most Okada riders in the study area were secondary school graduates (37.3%). Thus, graduate employment in the sector may be reasoned on the basis of unemployment in the country which may jeopardize the full realization of their potentials.

On the distribution of respondents' state of origin, the result shows that 39.6% of the respondents were from Edo State; 17.3% of the respondents were from Delta; 16.9% of the respondents were from Rivers; while others of the respondents were 17.3%. This indicates that majority of motorcycle operators were from Edo state. This implies that people who engage in commercial motorcyclist in the study area include both indigenes and non-indigenes of Edo state.

4.2 Challenges Associated with Commercial Motorcycle Business in Nigeria

The study objective is to examine the challenges associated with commercial motorcycle business in Nigeria. The ultimate goal is to understand the challenges facing commercial motorcyclists in the study areas and to know if they still want to continue in the profession.

Table 3: Challenges Associated with Commercial Motorcycle Business in Etsako LGA

How true is the argument that commercial motorcycling aids criminalities in the society	Frequency	Percentage
Very true	147	59.8
Not true	65	26.4
Indifference	34	13.8
Total	246	100.0
What kind of criminalities is Okada used for?	Frequency	Percentage
Kidnapping	78	37.7
Rape	29	14.0
Stealing	43	20.8
Other criminal act	57	27.5
Total	207	100.0
How true is the issue of recklessness in driving and non-compliance to traffic rules are challenges to okada riders ?	Frequency	Percentage
Very true	159	62.8
Not true	43	17.0
Indifference	51	20.2
Total	253	100.0
Some states like Lagos had banned the use of Okada riding on the major roads in Lagos. In your opinion what is responsible for such ban?	Frequency	Percentage
Frequent accident due to reckless riding	68	27.1
Non adherent to road signs and traffic regulations	55	21.9
Use of unregistered motorcycles for criminal activities	128	51.0
Total	251	100.0
Have you experienced any form of indiscriminate arrest by any of the state government and local government agents?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	226	89.3
No	27	10.7
Total	253	100.0
Do you experience incessant levy from state and local government revenue agents?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	248	98.0
No	4	1.6
Total	253	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2013)

Table 3 above presents the frequency distribution of respondents on challenges facing commercial motorcyclists in Edo state, Nigeria. The result shows that 59.8% of the respondents agree that commercial motorcyclist aids criminal activities, 26.4% disagree while 13.8% were indifferent. Thus, majority of the respondents agreed that commercial motorcycling (Okada) aid criminal activities in Edo state, Nigeria. This support the view of a forum organized by the ministry of transport in Lagos state which revealed that there have been cases of motorcycles (Okada) being use by armed robbers to deprive the citizens of their lifelong investments and valuable property. This is true of some cities in Nigeria where Okada has been banned from operation at certain hour of the day (nigeriannewsworld.com, 30th April, 2011).

Investigating the issue further, a respondent in an IDI session said:

This assertion is correct but I would want to let you know that most of those who perpetrate criminal activities are those who do not have attachment or registered with any affiliated unit. One of the major responsibilities of the association is to check the conduct of illegal okada riders who often infiltrate the business with the aim of perpetrating criminal activities. This is usually achieved through the issuance of identity cards and vest to registered

members of the association (IDI / Water beard, Auchu / Executive member/May, 2013).

Likewise another interviewee states:

Indeed, motorcycles are often use for criminal act; such as snatching of personal effect or belongings like bags, and phones, abduction and killings including raping of innocent people. Those who carry out such criminal act are people of questionable character and criminal minded riders who are not genuine commercial motorcyclists because they use unregistered motorcycles to carry out the evil act. However, a lot of activities and programmes have been put in place by the government and the union to curb the menace and to protect the image of true commercial motorcyclists in Edo state, Nigeria (IDI / Okada union chairman / Ighiku, Jattu /May, 2013).

Furthermore, the respondents were asked to mention one crime associated with commercial motorcycling profession in Edo state. The result shows that 37.7% of the respondents said kidnapping, 14.0% said raping, and 20.8% said stealing while 27.5% said other criminal act. The finding supports the view of Olubomehin (2012) who observed that various forms of criminal activities are perpetuated by commercial motorcycle operators in Nigeria.

The above finding is buttressed by a respondent during an IDI session, He said:

About eighty-five percent of crimes committed in Auchu are traceable to armed bandits who operate with motorcycles usually early in the morning and late at night. They act as commercial motorcyclists and carry passengers to places where they can steal from them. This is one of the reasons why government at state level banned the operation of commercial motorcycle from 8pm to 6 am in some part of Edo state (IDI/Igbe road, Auchu units/FRSC official/ May 2013).

From the above responses, it could be inferred that the use of motorcycles for criminal act by unregistered motorcycles is one of the major challenges facing the business of commercial motorcycle in Nigeria. Due to the assumption that commercial motorcyclists are perpetrators of dubious dealings and double-crossing of innocent passengers: snatching of personal effects like bags, phones, abduction and killing as well as raping of young girls, many commercial motorcyclists have been wrongly charged and punished for unknown crime. However, in recent times, this has been curbed through the issuance of identity cards and vest to registered members of the association.

Table 3 further shows that 62.8% of the respondents agreed that reckless driving and non-compliance to traffic rules by some commercial motorcyclists (Okada riders) is another challenge facing the business of commercial motorcycle in Nigeria, 17.0% disagrees while 20.2% were indifference. The finding corroborates the view of Olobomehin (2012) and Nderibe (2009) who observed that over the years, accidents due to the recklessness and refusal to comply with traffic rules by commercial motorcyclists (Okada) have being kept on increasing in direct proportion to the increase in the number of motorcycles operating for commercial purposes. Similarly, Akpan et., al (2011) reported that some commercial motorcyclists do constitute nuisance by showing lackadaisical attitudes to human lives and property. They further said that these attitudes can be attributed to inexperience, arrogance, pride, greed and frustration in life.

An interview with a Police officer revealed that:

One of the challenges facing commercial motorcycle profession in Edo state is safety as a result of their failure to obey

government regulations and traffic rules. Many of them don't use protective gadgets like helmet, sun glasses, and hand gloves when riding as well as non-compliance with traffic warden who gives signals on the road. Sometimes they ride recklessly without particulars. (IDI / Police / Iverekhu, South Ibie / May, 2013).

Another interviewee, a union executive confirmed the position above thus:

The union performs various functions one of which is to organize activities to enlighten the members on government regulations, safety and traffic rules on the high way. However, the problem of commercial motorcyclists (Okada riders) is caused by the impatient attitude of motor drivers. They over speed on high way and this make them lose controls which sometimes result in collision with commercial motorcyclists that lead to traffic accident, hospital admission and loss of lives (IDI / Okada union chairman / Ighiku, Jattu / May, 2013).

The inference that could be drawn here is that safety as a result of lack of protection and adequate clothing for drivers, reckless driving, impatient, over speeding and non-compliance to traffic rules is also a challenge facing commercial motorcyclists in Nigeria. The finding tallies with Akpan et., al (2011) and Olubomehin (2012) who reported that, the rise of commercial motorcyclists has been accompanied by increased levels of risk of accidents, bad behaviours, reckless driving, poor attitude of the operators and resistance to laudable government policies among others. As a result they have come under heavy scrutiny culminating in legislations restricting and in some instances prohibiting their operations in some cities.

Investigating this further, the respondents were asked to state the reason for the ban of commercial motorcyclists (Okada) operations in some states like Lagos, Nigeria. The result shows that 27.1% of the respondents said frequent accident due to reckless riding, 21.9% said non-adherent to road signs and traffic regulations, 51.0% said the use of unregistered motorcycles for criminal activities. However, majority of the respondents claimed that the use of unregistered motorcycles for criminal activities cause the ban of commercial motorcyclists in some state capitals in Nigeria.

Corroborating the above finding, an interviewee said:

The ban of commercial motorcyclists arises as a result of government response to criminal activities that accompanied the increase in numbers of motorcycles for business and private purposes. Lately, one of the popular musicians in Nigeria was killed by gun men on a motorcycle in Lagos state. Similarly, there are many reports on stealing, rape and kidnapping that was carried out with the use of motorcycles in some states in Nigeria. (IDI / Police / Iverekhu, South Ibie / May, 2013).

Buttressing the above statement another interviewee said:

More so, commercial motorcyclists are vulnerable road users because of their high injuries in the event of road crashes due to their over speeding, overloading and unprotected body. This explains why government banned it operations in some states of the federation. (IDI / Road Safety Official / Poly Unit, South Ibie / May, 2013).

From the response above, it is evident that the use of unregistered motorcycles for criminal activities, safety, reckless driving, over speeding, traffic accidents and injuries causes the ban of commercial motorcyclists and arrest of motorcyclists in some states in Nigeria. However, this has adversely affected the purpose of commercial motorcyclists as a means of employment generation, livelihood and family sustenance.

On the issue of indiscriminate arrest of commercial motorcyclists, it was found that 89.3% of the respondents admitted that they have been indiscriminately arrested while 10.7% disputed it.

In corroborating the finding, a union executive during IDI session said:

Honestly, commercial motorcyclists (Okada) experienced indiscriminate arrest by the law enforcement agents. However, the Motorcycle Transport Union protects the welfare of members as well ensure the enforcement of law and regulation. The union ensures that the law enforcement agents such as police and Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) do not take undue advantage of their members. Thus, our union always protects registered members whenever they are in trouble, particularly relating to careless attitudes of motor vehicle drivers. We make sure that no member is unfairly treated by the law enforcement agents like the police and Federal Road Safety Corpse (FRSC) (IDI / Okada union chairman / Auchi poly unit, south Ibie / May, 2013).

In contrast to the above statement, a police officer said:

It is far from truth that police officers and other law enforcement agents arrest commercial motorcyclists for no just cause. They are arrested when they have violated the law and are found guilty of an offence. Majority of the commercial motorcyclists do not have good driving experience, rider's license, and rides unregistered motorcycle as well as they use to take alcohol (referred to as *Paraga or Sepe*) when operating during the day. Therefore, they are often unaware of traffic rules and signs, and tend to overestimate their driving abilities which put them in trouble (IDI / Road Safety Official / Poly Unit, South Ibie / May, 2013)

The deduction that could be made from the above results and comments is that only few of the commercial motorcyclists are law abiding and have not been arrested for violating any of the traffic law and regulations in the study area. While majority of those that have been arrested for non-compliance with the traffic laws and regulations see the law enforcement agents (i.e the police and road safety officials etc.) as antagonists and unfriendly set of people.

On the issue of incessant levy from the state and local government agents, 98.0% of the respondents claimed that they experience incessant levy collection from the state and local government revenue agents, while 1.6% of the respondents dispute it. Thus, majority of the commercial motorcyclists (Okada) experienced incessant levy from the state and local government revenue agents.

Investigating the issue further, a respondent said:

The issue of levy is one of the problems facing this Okada business. We paid multiple levies to state and local government and our unions on daily basis. For instance, I spent close to 400 naira for the collection of rider's tickets and other permits daily, excluding the monthly association dues of 500 naira (IDI/ Male /Auchi Poly unit, South Ibie / May, 2013).

Another interviewee state:

Just two weeks ago, there was a protest over the increase in the daily levy by some commercial motorcyclists which was the third in the area in less than a month. The protest paralyzed commercial activities in the area for several hours as the protesting 'Okada riders' barricaded major junctions, causing workers, students, pupils and other users of their services to trek long distances to get to their destinations.... I think the issue of levy is a critical challenge that needs urgent address in Nigerian informal sector (IDI / Police / Iverekhu, South Ibie / May, 2013).

The deduction that could be made from the above responses and comments is that commercial motorcyclists are obliged to pay multiple tax and levies in the course of operations which often affect their expected daily income and earnings. As result of this, majority of commercial motorcyclists in the study area work round the clock as well as embarked on frequent public protest with social and economic implications.

Level of Job Satisfaction among commercial motorcyclists in Edo State

This objective measures level of satisfaction among Okada riders. The ultimate goal is to understand if commercial motorcyclists are satisfied with their occupation despite the numerous challenges encountered.

Table 4 Distribution of respondents according to their level of satisfaction with the commercial motorcycle

Describe your level of satisfaction with the commercial motorcycles operators despite the challenges	Frequency	Percentage
Very satisfactory	4	1.6
Satisfactory	60	23.7
Low satisfactory	189	74.7
Total	253	100.0
Do you combine commercial motorcycling with any vocation or business?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	239	93.7
No	4	1.6
Total	253	100.0
If your answer to question 4 is yes! Why are you combining commercial motorcycling with another vocation?	Frequency	Percentage
To earn more income	191	74.9
More passion for it	36	14.1
Intention to back out of Okada business	18	7.1
Total	245	100.0
Do you intend to quit commercial motorcycling business?	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	248	97.3
No	4	1.6
Total	252	252
If answer to question 6 is yes, why do you intend to quit?	Frequency	Percentage
To return back to my previous vocation	48	18.8
To go into another business	42	16.5
Because of risk involved	68	30.6
Health challenge	72	24.3
Stigmatization, multiple levies and harassment from law enforcement	21	8.2
Total	251	100.0

Source: Field survey (2013)

Table 4 above shows the respondents level of satisfaction with commercial motorcycling. The result shows that 25.3% of the respondents were very satisfy with the business while

74.7% of the respondents were low satisfaction. The majority of the respondents have low satisfaction with the business. The table also shows the responses of the respondents on combining Okada business with other vocation. The result shows that 93.7% of the respondents combine Okada business with other vocation; while 1.6% of the respondents did not. Thus, majority of the respondents combine the business (Okada) with other informal vocations.

Furthermore, table 4 also presents responses why respondents combine other occupation with Okada business. The result shows that 74.9% of the respondents said to earn more income; 14.1% of the respondents said because they have more passion for it; while 7.1% of the respondents said they have intention to go out of commercial motorcycling business. The results indicate that, the majority of the respondents combine other vocation to Okada business because of more income.

Also, table 4 shows responses to the question of intention to quit Okada business. The result shows that 97.3% of the respondents said yes to quit Okada business; while 1.6% of the respondents disagree. The majority of the respondents have intention to quit Okada business.

More so, table 4 reveals the result of why Okada operators intend to quit. The result shows that 18.8% of the respondents said to return back to their previous vocation; 16.5% of the respondents said to go into another business; 30.6% of the respondents said because of risk involved; 24.3% of the respondents said because of health challenge; while 8.2% of the respondents said because of stigmatization. The majority of the respondents said because of risk involved in riding Okada will make them quit Okada business.

Investigating the issue further, a respondent during IDI session asserted that:

Sometimes I still combine Okada business with my primary profession due to the fact that I want to earn sufficient income to take care of my financial need. This is because it is not every hours of the day that I have passengers to carry. When children have gone to schools and their parents gone to their working places I go back to my home to continue my primary occupation which is shoe making... This is because not every hour of the day those passengers are available. So I use that period to generate income from my primary occupation (IDI/igbe Road, Auchi/Okada rider/May, 2013)

Compliment the above interviewee:

I am a graduate and a tailor; I joined Okada business due to low patronage and lack of infrastructure. I am not satisfied with Okada business. There is no joy in riding Okada, because of the challenges involve such as health risk, harassment, stigmatization etc. But I don't have choice at the moment, I must survive with my family because am a married man. If I can get a good job today I will abandon Okada business. (Idi / Okada rider / Ap unit, Auchi / May, 2013).

Another compliment the respondents:

I don't think am interested in the business any longer. The daily earning is falling due to police arrest and harassment from road safety official. I want to abandon the business and return to my original occupation. I am a tailor. You see, the problem is low patronage and lack infrastructure. The government should help us improve electricity situation in Nigeria. Nigeria should encourage us by patronizing locally made product. The only way man is satisfy is when he sees his product being used and appreciate by others, not just the monetary benefit. (IDI / Okada rider / power line unit / May, 2013).

Another response:

None of us will tell you that he is satisfied with the job because of the challenges in the business. When you leave to work, the possibility of you coming home with your complete body is not guarantee. If you go to general hospital in Auchi, you will see many people lying in pain as a result of Okada accident. Also, the issue of social stigmatization from members of the public is another problem we are facing. People generally look down on us; they see Okada riders as people who cannot get better jobs in the society. (IDI / Okada rider / Igbe road unit, Auchi / May, 2013).

Compliment the above interviewee:

I am a shoemaker; I joined Okada business due to low patronage and lack of infrastructure. I am not satisfied with Okada business. There is no joy in riding Okada, because of the challenges involve such health, risk, stigmatization etc. But I don't have choice at the moment, I must survive with my family because am a married man. If I can get a good job today I will abandon Okada business. (IDI/ Okada rider / Ap unit, Auchi / May, 2013).

The above analysis shows there are feelings and attitude of job dissatisfaction with Okada business among the respondents. The dissatisfaction is can be connected with the challenges associated with Okada business especially the risk inherent in the business of commercial motorcycling which have sent many operators and commuters into untimely death while some have been eternally maimed. Also the problem of stigmatization and health challenges which is observed by the respondents in both the interview and questionnaire responses. This findings support the views of Olufayo (2006) and Olubomehin (2012) that workers are more likely to be dissatisfied with jobs that pose health and safety risk. Therefore, it can be inferred that Okada occupation in the study area is lucrative and serve as source of livelihood to operators yet, there is high level of challenges in the business.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study has within its scope investigates the challenges of commercial motorcyclists in Etsako West Local Government Area of Edo state, Nigeria. The study includes all classes of commercial motorcyclists; full-time and part time riders, in selected wards within the Etsako LGAs. A descriptive survey design with the aid of self-administered questionnaire and in-depth interview were used. A total number of two hundred and fifty-five questionnaire were distributed and 10 in-depth interviews were conducted which were analyzed using descriptive and content analyses. The findings revealed that the use of motorcycles for criminal activities by fake commercial motorcyclists, lack of protection and adequate vests for drivers, reckless driving, impatient, over speeding and non-compliance to traffic rules, ban and arrest of innocent motorcyclists, and payment of incessant levies are the major challenges of commercial motorcyclists in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are provided:

1. There should be development in the level of national security. This can be achieved by recruiting more trained and experienced law enforcement agents in Nigeria. By so doing, the menace of criminal activities, lack of safety, impatient, over speeding and non-compliance to traffic rules associated with commercial motorcyclists will be curtailed and the pedigree of genuine commercial motorcyclists will be protected in Nigeria.
2. Government should make policy that will enhance mandatory okada training of new commercial motorcyclists, rider's license, and registration of all commercial motorcyclists as well as regulation of motorcycles levy.

3. Government should provide employment for graduates, and worthwhile education scholarship for undergraduates and secondary school leavers who venture into the business due to frustration that results from unemployment and financial mishap.

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